

ON THE CONGRUENCE $N \equiv A \pmod{\varphi(N)}$

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Abstract

D. H. Lehmer asked whether there are any composite integers for which $\varphi(n) \mid n - 1$, where φ is the Euler function. In this paper, we show that the number of such integers $n \leq x$ is $o(x^{1/2})$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$.

1. Introduction

Let $\varphi(n)$ be the *Euler function*, which is defined as usual by

$$\varphi(n) = n \prod_{p \mid n} (1 - p^{-1}) \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}).$$

In 1932, D. H. Lehmer [4] asked whether there are any *composite* numbers n for which $\varphi(n) \mid n - 1$, and the answer to this question is still unknown.

In what follows, for any set $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ we put $\mathcal{S}(x) = \mathcal{S} \cap [1, x]$ for all $x \geq 1$. In a series of papers (see [5, 6, 7]) C. Pomerance considered the problem of bounding the cardinality of $\mathcal{L}(x)$, where \mathcal{L} is the (possibly empty) set of composite numbers n such that $\varphi(n) \mid n - 1$.

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In his third paper, Pomerance [7] established the bound

$$\#\mathcal{L}(x) \ll x^{1/2}(\log x)^{3/4} \tag{1.1}$$

and remarked:

There is still clearly a wide gap between the possibility that $\mathcal{L} = \emptyset$ and (1.1), for the latter does not even establish that the members of \mathcal{L} are as scarce as squares!

Refinements of the underlying method of [7] led to subsequent improvements of the bound (1.1):

$$\#\mathcal{L}(x) \ll x^{1/2}(\log x)^{1/2}(\log \log x)^{-1/2} \tag{Shan [8]}$$

$$\#\mathcal{L}(x) \ll x^{1/2}(\log \log x)^{1/2} \tag{Banks and Luca [1]}.$$

In the present note, we use similar techniques to show that the members of \mathcal{L} are *scarcer than squares*, i.e., that $\#\mathcal{L}(x) = o(x^{1/2})$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$. More precisely, we prove the following:

Theorem 1. *For any fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ the bound*

$$\#\mathcal{L}(x) \ll \frac{x^{1/2}}{(\log x)^{\Theta-\varepsilon}}$$

holds, where $\Theta = 0.129398\dots$ is the least positive solution to the equation

$$2\Theta(\log \Theta - 1 - \log \log 2) = -\log 2. \tag{1.2}$$

As in the earlier papers [1, 5, 6, 7, 8] where bounds on the cardinality of $\mathcal{L}(x)$ are given, Theorem 1 admits a natural generalization. For an arbitrary integer a , let

$$\mathcal{L}_a = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : n \equiv a \pmod{\varphi(n)}\},$$

and put

$$\mathcal{L}'_a = \{n \in \mathcal{L}_a : n \neq pa \text{ for } p \text{ prime, } p \nmid a\}.$$

Since $\mathcal{L}'_1 = \mathcal{L} \cup \{1\}$, Theorem 1 is the special case $a = 1$ of the following:

Theorem 2. *Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ be fixed. Then,*

$$\#\mathcal{L}'_a(x) \ll \frac{x^{1/2}}{(\log x)^{\Theta-\varepsilon}},$$

where Θ is the least positive solution to the equation (1.2).

We remark that for $a = 0$ one has $\#\mathcal{L}'_0(x) \asymp (\log x)^2$, which follows from the result of Sierpiński [9, p. 232]:

$$\mathcal{L}'_0 = \{1\} \cup \{2^i 3^j : i \geq 1, j \geq 0\}.$$

Hence, we shall assume that $a \neq 0$ in the sequel.

2. Preliminaries

According to [7, Lemma 1] the inequality

$$\#\mathcal{L}'_a(x) \leq 4a^2 + \sum_{d|a} \#\mathcal{L}''_{a/d}(x/d)$$

holds, where

$$\mathcal{L}''_a = \{n \in \mathcal{L}'_a : n \text{ is square-free}\}.$$

Thus, to prove Theorem 2 it suffices to show that

$$\#\mathcal{L}''_a(x) \ll \frac{x^{1/2}}{(\log x)^{\Theta-\varepsilon}}. \tag{2.1}$$

The following result is due to Pomerance [7, Theorem 1]:

Lemma 1. *Suppose that $n \geq 16a^2$, $n \in \mathcal{L}''_a$, and $K = \omega(n)$. Let the prime factorization of n be $p_1 \cdots p_K$, where $p_1 > \cdots > p_K$. Then, for $1 \leq i \leq K$ we have*

$$p_i < (i + 1) \left(1 + \prod_{j=i+1}^K p_j \right).$$

We also need the following lemma from [8]:

Lemma 2. *Suppose that $\delta \geq 0$, $a_1 \geq \cdots \geq a_t = 0$, and $a_i \leq \delta + \sum_{j=i+1}^t a_j$ for $1 \leq i \leq t - 1$. Then, for any real number ρ such that $0 \leq \rho < \sum_{i=1}^t a_i$, there is a subset \mathcal{I} of $\{1, \dots, t\}$ such that $\rho - \delta < \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} a_i \leq \rho$.*

Our principal tool is the next lemma, which is a simplified and weakened version of [2, Proposition 3]. For convenience, our lemma is stated in terms of $\log \log n$ rather than $\log \log x$ as in [2], but this change is easily justified in view of the term $(\log x)^{o(1)}$ that we include in our estimates.

Lemma 3. *For fixed $0 < \lambda < 1$, the counting function of the set*

$$\mathcal{V}_\lambda = \{n : \omega(n) < \lambda \log \log n\}$$

satisfies the bound

$$\#\mathcal{V}_\lambda(x) \leq \frac{x}{(\log x)^{1+\lambda \log(\lambda/\varepsilon)+o(1)}} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

For fixed $\lambda > 1$, the counting function of the set

$$\mathcal{W}_\lambda = \{n : \omega(n) > \lambda \log \log n\}$$

satisfies the bound

$$\#\mathcal{W}_\lambda(x) \leq \frac{x}{(\log x)^{1+\lambda \log(\lambda/\varepsilon)+o(1)}} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Finally, we recall the well-known inequality of Landau [3]:

$$\frac{n}{\varphi(n)} \ll \log \log n \quad (n \geq 3). \tag{2.2}$$

3. Proof of Theorem 2

We write the bound of [1] in the form:

$$\#\mathcal{L}''_a(x) \leq \#\mathcal{L}'_a(x) \leq x^{1/2}(\log x)^{o(1)} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty). \tag{3.1}$$

Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be a small fixed parameter. Let α and β be fixed real numbers such that

$$\Theta - \varepsilon < \alpha/2 < \beta < \Theta,$$

where Θ is defined as in Theorem 1, and put

$$A = (\log x)^\alpha \quad \text{and} \quad B = (\log x)^\beta.$$

Note that (3.1) implies

$$\#\mathcal{L}''_a(x/A) \leq x^{1/2}(\log x)^{-\alpha/2+o(1)} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty),$$

and since $\alpha/2 > \Theta - \varepsilon$ it follows that

$$\#\mathcal{L}''_a(x/A) \ll x^{1/2}(\log x)^{-\Theta+\varepsilon}. \tag{3.2}$$

Now let $n \in \mathcal{L}''_a$ be fixed with $16a^2 \leq x/A < n \leq x$. Put $K = \omega(n)$, and factor $n = p_1 \cdots p_K$ where $p_1 > \dots > p_K$. By Lemma 1 we have

$$\log p_i < \log(2K) + \sum_{j=i+1}^K \log p_j \quad (1 \leq i \leq K).$$

Applying Lemma 2 with $\delta = \log(2K)$, $t = K + 1$, $a_i = \log p_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq K$, $a_t = 0$, and $\rho = \log(x^{1/2}/B)$, we conclude that n has a positive divisor d such that $\rho - \delta < \log d \leq \rho$; in other words,

$$\frac{x^{1/2}}{2\omega(n)B} \leq d \leq \frac{x^{1/2}}{B}. \tag{3.3}$$

Setting $m = n/d$, it is also clear that

$$\frac{x^{1/2}B}{A} \leq m \leq 2\omega(n)Bx^{1/2}. \tag{3.4}$$

First, suppose that $n \in \mathcal{W}_{20}$. Since n is square-free we have

$$\omega(d) + \omega(m) = \omega(dm) = \omega(n) > 20 \log \log n,$$

hence either $d \in \mathcal{W}_{10}$ or $m \in \mathcal{W}_{10}$. Using the trivial bound $\omega(n) \leq 2 \log x$ and the inequality $A \leq B^2$, we see that n has a divisor $k \in \mathcal{W}_{10}$ such that

$$\frac{x^{1/2}}{4B \log x} \leq k \leq 4Bx^{1/2} \log x.$$

Note that $\gcd(k, \varphi(k)) \mid a$ since $k \mid n$ and $n \equiv a \pmod{\varphi(n)}$. On the other hand, if k is fixed with the above properties, and n is a number in \mathcal{L}_a that is divisible by k , then

$$n \equiv 0 \pmod{k} \quad \text{and} \quad n \equiv a \pmod{\varphi(k)}.$$

By the Chinese Remainder Theorem, we see that n is uniquely determined modulo $\text{lcm}[k, \varphi(k)]$. Hence, the number of integers $n \leq x$ with $n \in \mathcal{L}_a'' \cap \mathcal{W}_{20}$ and $k \mid n$ does not exceed

$$1 + \frac{x}{\text{lcm}[k, \varphi(k)]} \leq 1 + \frac{xa}{k\varphi(k)} \ll 1 + \frac{x \log \log x}{k^2},$$

where we have used (2.2) in the last step. Put $y = x^{1/2}/(4B \log x)$ and $z = 4Bx^{1/2} \log x$. Summing the contributions over all such integers k , we derive that

$$\begin{aligned} \#\{n \in \mathcal{L}_a'' \cap \mathcal{W}_{20} : x/A \leq n \leq x\} &\ll \sum_{\substack{y \leq k \leq z \\ k \in \mathcal{W}_{10}}} \left(1 + \frac{x \log \log x}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \sum_{\substack{k \leq z \\ k \in \mathcal{W}_{10}}} 1 + x \log \log x \sum_{\substack{k \geq y \\ k \in \mathcal{W}_{10}}} \frac{1}{k^2} \\ &\ll \frac{z}{(\log z)^{14}} + \frac{x \log \log x}{y(\log y)^{14}}. \end{aligned}$$

Here, we have used Lemma 3, the inequality $1 + 10 \log(10/e) > 14$, and the estimate

$$\sum_{\substack{k \geq y \\ k \in \mathcal{W}_\lambda}} \frac{1}{k^2} \ll \frac{1}{y(\log y)^{1+\lambda \log(\lambda/e)+o(1)}} \quad (y \rightarrow \infty),$$

which follows from Lemma 3 by partial summation. Inserting the definitions of y , z and B into the bound above, and noting that $\beta < \Theta < 1$, we derive that

$$\begin{aligned} \#\{n \in \mathcal{L}_a'' \cap \mathcal{W}_{20} : x/A \leq n \leq x\} &\ll \frac{Bx^{1/2} \log \log x}{(\log x)^{13}} \\ &\ll x^{1/2} (\log x)^{\beta-12} \\ &\ll x^{1/2} (\log x)^{-\Theta}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

Next, we consider the case that $n \notin \mathcal{W}_{20}$. Since $\omega(n) \leq 20 \log \log x$, the inequalities (3.3) and (3.4) can be replaced by

$$\frac{x^{1/2}}{40B \log \log x} \leq d \leq \frac{x^{1/2}}{B} \tag{3.6}$$

and

$$\frac{x^{1/2}B}{A} \leq m \leq 40Bx^{1/2} \log \log x, \tag{3.7}$$

respectively. Let \mathcal{T} be the collection of pairs (d, m) of natural numbers such that $dm \in \mathcal{L}_a''$ and the inequalities (3.6) and (3.7) hold. Then,

$$\#\{n \in \mathcal{L}_a'' \setminus \mathcal{W}_{20} : x/A \leq n \leq x\} \leq \#\mathcal{T}. \tag{3.8}$$

Lemma 4. *If x is sufficiently large, then for every integer m there is at most one integer d such that $(d, m) \in \mathcal{T}$.*

Proof. Suppose (d_1, m) and (d_2, m) both lie in \mathcal{T} . Since d_1m and d_2m are numbers in \mathcal{L}_a'' , we have

$$\varphi(m) \mid d_1m - a \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi(m) \mid d_2m - a.$$

Hence it follows that

$$d_1 \equiv d_2 \pmod{\varphi(m)/\mu}, \tag{3.9}$$

where $\mu = \gcd(m, \varphi(m))$; note that $\mu \ll 1$ since $\mu \mid a$. By (3.6) we have the bound

$$\max\{d_1, d_2\} \leq \frac{x^{1/2}}{B} = x^{1/2}(\log x)^{-\beta},$$

whereas by (2.2) and (3.7) we have

$$\frac{\varphi(m)}{\mu} \gg \frac{m}{\log \log m} \geq x^{1/2}(\log x)^{\beta-\alpha+o(1)} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Since $\beta > \alpha/2$, it follows that for all sufficiently large x , both d_1 and d_2 are smaller than the modulus in (3.9), so the congruence becomes an equality $d_1 = d_2$. This completes the proof. \square

From now on, we assume that x is large enough to yield the conclusion of Lemma 4. Let \mathcal{M} denote the set of integers m such that $(d, m) \in \mathcal{T}$ for some integer d . By Lemma 4, the map $(d, m) \mapsto m$ provides a bijection $\mathcal{T} \xrightarrow{\sim} \mathcal{M}$; in particular, $\#\mathcal{T} = \#\mathcal{M}$, and (3.8) can be restated as

$$\#\{n \in \mathcal{L}_a'' \setminus \mathcal{W}_{20} : x/A \leq n \leq x\} \leq \#\mathcal{M}. \tag{3.10}$$

Let $\vartheta = 0.373365\dots$ be the unique solution in the interval $(0, 1)$ to the equation

$$1 + \vartheta \log(\vartheta/e) = \vartheta \log 2.$$

From (1.2) it follows that

$$2\Theta = 1 + \vartheta \log(\vartheta/e) = \vartheta \log 2. \tag{3.11}$$

We now express \mathcal{M} as a disjoint union $\mathcal{M}_1 \cup \mathcal{M}_2$, where

$$\mathcal{M}_1 = \mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{V}_\vartheta \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{M}_2 = \mathcal{M} \setminus \mathcal{V}_\vartheta.$$

Using Lemma 3, (3.7) and (3.11) we derive the bound

$$\#\mathcal{M}_1 \leq \#\mathcal{V}_\vartheta(40Bx^{1/2} \log \log x) = x^{1/2}(\log x)^{\beta-2\Theta+o(1)} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Since $\beta < \Theta$, it follows that

$$\#\mathcal{M}_1 \ll x^{1/2}(\log x)^{-\Theta}. \tag{3.12}$$

Lemma 5. *If x is sufficiently large, then for every integer d there is at most one integer $m \in \mathcal{M}_2$ such that $(d, m) \in \mathcal{T}$.*

Proof. Suppose (d, m_1) and (d, m_2) both lie in \mathcal{T} , where $m_1, m_2 \in \mathcal{M}_2$. From the lower bound of (3.7) we see that both numbers m_1 and m_2 have at least $\kappa = \lfloor \vartheta \log \log(x^{1/2}B/A) \rfloor$ distinct odd prime divisors; hence both integers $\varphi(m_1)$ and $\varphi(m_2)$ are divisible by 2^κ . Since dm_1 and dm_2 are numbers in \mathcal{L}''_a , we can write

$$dm_1 = a + 2^\kappa \varphi(d) s_1 \quad \text{and} \quad dm_2 = a + 2^\kappa \varphi(d) s_2$$

for some natural numbers s_1, s_2 . Hence it follows that

$$m_1 \equiv m_2 \pmod{2^\kappa \varphi(d)/\mu} \tag{3.13}$$

where $\mu = \gcd(d, 2^\kappa \varphi(d))$; as before we have $\mu \ll 1$ since $\mu \mid a$. By (3.7) we have the bound

$$\max\{m_1, m_2\} \leq 40Bx^{1/2} \log \log x = x^{1/2}(\log x)^{\beta+o(1)} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

On the other hand, since $\kappa = (\vartheta + o(1)) \log \log x$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$, using (2.2), (3.6) and (3.11) we derive the lower bound

$$\frac{2^\kappa \varphi(d)}{\mu} \gg \frac{d \cdot 2^\kappa}{\log \log d} \geq \frac{x^{1/2}(\log x)^{\vartheta \log 2 + o(1)}}{B(\log \log x)^2} = x^{1/2}(\log x)^{2\Theta - \beta + o(1)}.$$

Since $\beta < \Theta$, it follows that $2^\kappa \varphi(d)/\mu > \max\{m_1, m_2\}$ once x is sufficiently large. The congruence (3.13) then becomes an equality $m_1 = m_2$, which finishes the proof. \square

We now assume that x is large enough to yield the conclusion of Lemma 5. Let \mathcal{D} denote the set of integers d such that $(d, m) \in \mathcal{T}$ for some integer $m \in \mathcal{M}_2$. Applying Lemma 5 and using the upper bound of (3.6), we see that

$$\#\mathcal{M}_2 = \#\mathcal{D} \leq \frac{x^{1/2}}{B} = x^{1/2}(\log x)^{-\beta}.$$

Since $\beta > \Theta - \varepsilon$ we obtain

$$\#\mathcal{M}_2 \leq x^{1/2}(\log x)^{-\Theta + \varepsilon}. \tag{3.14}$$

Combining (3.2), (3.5), (3.10), (3.12) and (3.14), and taking into account that $\#\mathcal{M} = \#\mathcal{M}_1 + \#\mathcal{M}_2$, we derive the bound (2.1), and this finishes the proof of Theorem 2.

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